

INVESTIGATING THE INFLUENCE OF GENDER AND ETIOLOGY ON PREVALENCE OF OSMF

Dr. Prapti Prashant Kole¹, Dr. Prafulla Gaikwad², Dr. Akshay Mishra³, Dr. Sanchi Kadbe⁴,
Dr. Revati Manoj Khandare⁵, Dr. Pavan Sable⁶

¹Junior Resident

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital

Wanadongri road, Nagpur-441110

²Professor and Head of Department

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital

Wanadongri road, Nagpur-441110

³Professor

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital

Wanadongri road, Nagpur-441110

⁴Senior Lecturer

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital

Wanadongri road, Nagpur-441110

⁵ Junior Resident

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital

Wanadongri road, Nagpur-441110

⁶ Junior Resident

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital

Wanadongri road, Nagpur-441110

Correspondence to:

Dr. Prapti Prashant Kole

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital

Wanadongri road, Nagpur-441110

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF) is a chronic, progressive disease characterized by fibrosis of the oral mucosa, leading to limited mouth opening and potentially malignant transformation. Vidarbha, a region in Maharashtra, India, has been reported to have a high prevalence of OSMF, possibly due to use of areca nut and tobacco (gutkha) in this region. Understanding the incidence and trends of OSMF cases in Vidarbha is crucial for effective preventive and management strategies.

Methods: A retrospective study was conducted to determine the incidence of OSMF cases over a 12-year period from 2012 to 2024 till date. Data was collected from records in Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery department at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur. Information on patient habits such as areca nut, tobacco (gutkha), grading, and management was collected and analyzed.

Results: The study identified a total of 907 cases of OSMF from Vidarbha to the institute during the study period. The majority of cases were in the age group of 18 to 40 years, and there was a male predominance. Although the etiology of OSMF is unclear, chewing apart from tobacco and arecanut contributes significantly. Clinical presentation varied from mild to severe fibrosis, with varying degrees of mouth opening restriction. Treatment varied depending on the stages of fibrosis.

Conclusion: The study highlights the significant burden of OSMF, with areca nut and tobacco consumption being major contributing factors. Public health interventions focusing on awareness about the harmful effects of these habits, prevention, early detection, and appropriate management are essential.

INTRODUCTION:

Oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF) was first described by Schwartz in the year 1952 as 'Atropica Idiopathica Mucosae Oris' and it was later renamed by Joshi in 1953 as 'Submucous fibrosis'. Various names have been attributed to this precancerous condition such as 'idiopathic scleroderma of mouth', 'idiopathic palatal fibrosis', 'sclerosing stomatitis', 'juxta epithelial fibrosis'.^{1,2} OSMF is a chronic, progressive, scarring disease, that predominantly affects people of South-East Asia region.³ Its onset is insidious over two to five years with initial symptoms such as burning sensation of mouth on eating spicy food, blisters usually on the palate, oral ulcerations with recurrent oral inflammation and dryness of the mouth. With progression the oral mucosa becomes blanched and slightly opaque and white bands appear. The white band may be dense and appear on faucial pillars, pterygomandibular raphe, buccal mucosa and around the mouth which may lead to reduced mouth opening and sometimes shortening or deviation of uvula.^{4,5}

Various epidemiological studies have shown that chewing betel nut is one of the most significant risk factors for OSMF with other factors such as autoimmunity, vitamin B, C, and iron deficiencies, chewing betel nut, consumption of spicy foods, human papilloma virus (HPV) infection, and genetic mutations.⁶ Various studies have been conducted in various parts of India to find out the burden of OSMF and its etiologic factors.⁷⁻¹⁰ But studies on prevalence of OSMF particularly in Maharashtra are limited. Thus this retrospective study is targeted to find out the influence of etiology and gender on the prevalence of OSMF in Vidarbha region of Maharashtra.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A retrospective study was conducted to determine the incidence of OSMF cases over a 12-year period from 2012 to 2024 till date. Data was collected from records in Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery department at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur. Information on patient habits such as areca nut, tobacco (gutkha) and gender were collected and analyzed. A total of 2927 patients reported between the study period, out of which 907 patients reported back for the treatment. This investigation was based on manual search and data extraction from patient medical records.

RESULTS:

The study identified a total of 907 cases of OSMF from Vidarbha to the institute during the study period. The majority of cases were in the age group of 18 to 40 years, and there was a male predominance. Although the etiology of OSMF is unclear, kharra chewing apart from tobacco and areca nut contributes significantly.

Table 1, Fig. 1 provides the hospital-based incidence rate of oral submucous fibrosis according to gender. The incidence rate in males range from 0.60 to 5.49 per 1000 patients in the non-pandemic years, while it increased to 22.37 per 1000 patients during second wave of pandemic. The rate in females range from 0.15 to 1.39 per 1000 patients, except during 2021, the rate increased to 4.47 per 1000 patients due to reduced number of patients attending the hospital during pandemic. Overall, across years, the incidence rate was higher among males as compared to females.

Table 1: Gender wise hospital-based incidence oral submucous fibrosis across years per 1000 patients

Year	MALE			FEMALE		
	Incidence rate / 1000 patients	95% CI		Incidence rate / 1000 patients	95% CI	
		Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
2012	2.79	2.07	3.68	0.45	0.19	0.88
2013	3.24	2.46	4.17	0.77	0.42	1.29
2014	4.05	3.19	5.07	0.64	0.33	1.12
2015	2.87	2.12	3.79	0.64	0.32	1.15
2016	4.35	3.44	5.43	0.67	0.35	1.17
2017	4.23	3.32	5.31	0.80	0.44	1.34
2018	4.87	3.87	6.04	0.77	0.41	1.32
2019	0.60	0.26	1.18	0.15	0.02	0.54
2020	1.84	0.68	4.01	0.92	0.19	2.69
2021	22.37	17.99	27.50	4.47	2.65	7.07
2022	5.49	4.36	6.81	1.00	0.56	1.66
2023	4.73	3.73	5.92	1.00	0.57	1.62
2024	5.40	3.67	7.66	1.39	0.60	2.74

Figure 1: Line plot with error bars showing gender wise hospital-based incidence rate of oral submucous fibrosis

In the present study, various predisposing factors contributing to the development of Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) were identified among the study population in the Vidarbha region. The most common factor was the use of smokeless forms of tobacco, particularly **kharra** and **gutkha**, which combine areca nut and tobacco with other substances such as lime, catechu, and pan extracts. Other contributory factors included **excessive consumption of chillies and spices**, and **iron deficiency anaemia**, both prevalent in the region.

Based on the responses from participants (n=100), the distribution of etiological factors is shown below:

Etiological Factor	Percentage (%)
Gutkha (areca nut + tobacco + others)	35%
Kharra (areca nut + tobacco)	25%
Chillies and Spices	15%
Iron Deficiency Anaemia	10%
Areca nut (independent use)	10%
Other (lime, catechu, pan extracts, etc.)	5%

Figure 2: Pie diagram depicting etiology for OSMF

DISCUSSION:

In the present retrospective study there was a male predominance for the incidence of OSMF from the year 2012 to 2024. The incidence rate in males ranged between 0.60 to 5.49 per 1000 patients in the non-pandemic years, while it increased to 22.37 per 1000 patients during second wave of pandemic. The rate in females ranged between 0.15 to 1.39 per 1000 patients, except during 2021, the rate increased to 4.47 per 1000 patients due to reduced number of patients attending the hospital. Overall, across years, the incidence rate was higher among males as compared to females. Our findings are in contrast to the study done by Sirsat and Khanolkar in Mumbai where they found male to female ratio of 1:1¹¹.

However, there are various other studies that have shown male predominance as correlating to our study such as a study by Wahi et al. who found male to female ratio of 2:1 and later Shah and Sharma 1.8:1.^{12,13} A study by Ahmad MS et al. also showed male predominance similar to our study.¹⁰ In the present study the reason for less incidence of OSMF in females might be more consciousness about health and esthetic values or hesitation to ask vendors for gutkha products.

Chillies and spices are one of the predisposing factors for the development of OSMF found in various studies. Chillies damage the cells of the mucosa and with prolonged exposure may lead to chronic inflammation and fibrosis.¹⁴⁻¹⁸ Chillies and spices are used on a large scale in the Vidarbha region.¹⁹ The use of arecanut and tobacco in the smokeless form is one of most important reason for development of OSMF. Other agents such as lime, catechu, pan extracts are also found to be the causative agents for OSMF.²⁰

Lysyl oxidase, a metallo enzyme of copper, secreted by fibroblasts initiates cross-linking of the collagen which makes it difficult to digest by mammalian fibroblasts. Areca nut contains high content of copper which may trigger the change in the collagen degradation and may lead to excessive accumulation collagen which in turn leads to permanent change in the fibroblast population and abnormal accumulation of collagen.²¹ Kharra is most commonly used smokeless form of tobacco in the vidarbha region which contains a mixture of areca nut and tobacco.²² Apart from this Gutkha which contains arecanut, tobacco, lime, catechu, pan extracts and other flavouring agents is also used in this region.²³ Iron deficiency anaemia can also be a cause of OSMF.²⁴ There is a high prevalence of iron deficiency anaemia in vidarbha region.²⁵ Moreover the habit-forming process of gutkha chewers is due to tobacco and areca nut, which if consumed for longer duration and frequencies is responsible for causing addiction, leading to

OSMF.¹⁰ According to some studies the cessation of use of areca nut and tobacco did not lead to the reversal of OSMF.²⁶⁻²⁸ In contrast a study by Avon et al. found improvement with cessation of use of areca nut.²⁹

CONCLUSION:

Thus the present study concluded that there is a significant burden of OSMF in the Vidarbha region especially owing to the practice of chewing Kharra and males are affected more than the females due to various reasons such as readily availability of arecanut and tobacco products to the males and health or esthetic concerns on part of the females.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS:

There are no acknowledgment and disclosure statements by author side.

FUNDING SOURCES:

There are no funding sources.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

There is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Munde A, Nayak P, Mishra S, Karle R, Farooqui A, Sawade R, Deshpande A. Demographic and clinical Profile of oral Submucous fibrosis: a retrospective study.
- [2] More CB, Gupta S, Joshi J, Varma SN. Classification system for oral submucous fibrosis. Journal of Indian Academy of Oral Medicine and Radiology. 2012;24(1):24.
- [3] Kumar KK, Saraswathi TR, Ranganathan K, Devi MU, Elizabeth J. Oral submucous fibrosis: A clinico-histopathological study in Chennai. Indian journal of dental research. 2007 Jul 1;18(3):106-11.
- [4] Passi D, Bhanot P, Kacker D, Chahal D, Atri M, Panwar Y. Oral submucous fibrosis: Newer proposed classification with critical updates in pathogenesis and management strategies. National journal of maxillofacial surgery. 2017 Jul 1;8(2):89-94.
- [5] More CB, Rao NR. Proposed clinical definition for oral submucous fibrosis. Journal of oral biology and craniofacial research. 2019 Oct 1;9(4):311-4.
- [6] Shih YH, Wang TH, Shieh TM, Tseng YH. Oral submucous fibrosis: a review on etiopathogenesis, diagnosis, and therapy. International journal of molecular sciences. 2019 Jun 16;20(12):2940.
- [7] Srivastava R, Jyoti B, Pradhan D, Siddiqui Z. Prevalence of oral submucous fibrosis in patients visiting dental OPD of a dental college in Kanpur: A demographic study. Journal of family medicine and primary care. 2019 Aug 28;8(8):2612-7.
- [8] Rani P, Singh RN, Sharma S, Shahi AK, Chandra S, Singh B. Prevalence of oral submucous fibrosis, its correlation of clinical grading to various habit factors among patients of bihar: a cross sectional study. Journal of Pharmacy and Bioallied Sciences. 2023 Jul 1;15(Suppl 1):S554-7.
- [9] Wei C, Shen X, Liu W, Du R. A scientometric study on research trends and characteristics of oral submucous fibrosis. Journal of Dental Sciences. 2024 May 18.
- [10] Ahmad MS, Ali SA, Ali AS, Chaubey KK. Epidemiological and etiological study of oral submucous fibrosis among gutkha chewers of Patna, Bihar, India. Journal of indian society of pedodontics and preventive dentistry. 2006 Apr 1;24(2):84-9.
- [11] Sirsat SM, Khanolkar VR. Submucous Fibrosis of the Palate and Pillars of the Fauces. Indian J Med Sci 1962;16:188-97.

- [12] Wahi PN, Kapur VL, Luthra UK, Srivastava MC. Submucous fibrosis of the oral cavity. 2. Studies on epidemiology. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 1966;35(5):793.
- [13] Shah N, Sharma PP. Role of chewing and smoking habits in the etiology of oral submucous fibrosis (OSF): a case-control study. *Journal of oral pathology & medicine*. 1998 Nov;27(10):475-9.
- [14] Shiau YY, Kwan HW. Submucous fibrosis in Taiwan. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology*. 1979 May 1;47(5):453-7.
- [15] McGurk M, Craig GT. Oral submucous fibrosis: two cases of malignant transformation in Asian immigrants to the United Kingdom. *British Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*. 1984 Feb 1;22(1):56-64.
- [16] Rajendran R. Oral submucous fibrosis: etiology, pathogenesis, and future research. *Bulletin of the World health organization*. 1994;72(6):985.
- [17] Pillai R, Balam P, Reddiar KS. Pathogenesis of oral submucous fibrosis. Relationship to risk factors associated with oral cancer. *Cancer*. 1992 Apr 15;69(8):2011-20.
- [18] VanWyk CW. Oral submucous fibrosis. The South African experience. *Indian Journal of Dental Research: Official Publication of Indian Society for Dental Research*. 1997 Apr 1;8(2):39-45.
- [19] Jagtap PP, Shingane US, Kulkarni KP. Economics of chilli production in India. *African Journal of Basic & Applied Sciences*. 2012;4(5):161-4.
- [20] Babu S, Bhat RV, Kumar PU, Sesikaran B, Rao KV, Aruna P, et al. A comparative clinico-pathological study of oral submucous fibrosis in habitual chewers of panmasala and betel quid. *ClinToxicol* 1996;34:317-22
- [21] Ma RH, Tsai CC, Shieh TY. Increased lysyl oxidase activity in fibroblasts cultured from oral submucous fibrosis associated with betel nut chewing in Taiwan. *Journal of oral pathology & medicine*. 1995 Oct;24(9):407-12.
- [22] Rathod S, Wanikar I, Raj A, Maske S, Harkare V. Association between kharra chewing and periodontal health status in oral submucous fibrosis patients of Central India, Nagpur. *Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology*. 2018 Jul 1;22(4):345-7.
- [23] Kuthe S, Maldhure S, Nimbalkar G. To Study the Prevalence of Areca Nut Induced Oral Submucous Fibrosis in Patients Visiting Dental OPD of ShalinitaiMeghe Hospital and Research Center Nagpur: A Demographic Study. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*. 2020 Oct 29;14(4):6351-7.
- [24] Bhattacharya PT, Khaite T, Sarkar SB, Sinha R. Oral submucous fibrosis secondary to iron deficiency anemia: a case report, etiopathogenesis and management. *The Journal of nutrition, health and aging*. 2016 Feb 1;20(2):205-8.
- [25] Dhurde VS, Patel AB, Locks LM, Hibberd PL. Anaemia prevalence, its determinants and profile of micronutrient status among rural school adolescent girls aged 14–19 years: a cross-sectional study in Nagpur district, Maharashtra, India. *Public Health Nutrition*. 2024 Jan;27(1):e248.
- [26] Seedat HA, Van Wyk CW. Submucous fibrosis (SF) in exbetel nut chewers: A report of 14 cases. *Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine*. 1988 May;17(5):226-9.
- [27] Murti PR, Gupta PC, Bhonsle RB, Daftary DK, Mehta FS, Pindborg JJ. Effect on the incidence of oral submucous fibrosis of intervention in the areca nut chewing habit. *Journal of oral pathology & medicine*. 1990 Feb;19(2):99-100.
- [28] Jayanthi V, Probert CS, Sher KS, Mayberry JF. Oral submucosal fibrosis--a preventable disease. *Gut*. 1992 Jan;33(1):4.
- [29] Avon SL. Oral mucosal lesions associated with use of quid. *Journal (Canadian Dental Association)*. 2004 Apr;70(4):244-8.